

A beginner's guide to weak gravity conjecture

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Abstract

This article discusses about the evolution of the weak gravity conjecture, from its original formulation to the different forms for axions and lattice charges and the recent developments for each of them. In addition, I discuss a possible relation between computability theory and sublattice weak gravity conjecture for homology spheres.

1 A preliminary introduction

The weak gravity conjecture is a conjecture of quantum gravity, broadly stated as that there exists a upper bound on the gravitational strength relative to the gauge forces in any consistent theory of quantum gravity [1]. This is reminiscent in the classical case [1]; for example, let us consider two objects of identical mass m and charge q at a distance r placed in vacuum. The Newtonian gravitational force of attraction between them is given by $F_G = \frac{Gm^2}{r^2}$ and the Coulombic force of repulsion between them is given by $F_E = \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2}$, G being the universal gravitational constant and ϵ_0 being the electrical permittivity in free space. For the gravitational force to be less than the force of repulsion,

$$\frac{Gm^2}{r^2} < \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} \rightarrow \left(\frac{q}{m}\right) > \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0 G} \quad (1)$$

The constant $\sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0 G} = 8.62 \times 10^{-11} C/kg$ is really small lower bound though; for example, for a proton, which has charge $1.6 \times 10^{-19} C$ and mass $9.1 \times 10^{-31} kg$, the specific charge is really $1.76 \times 10^{11} C/kg$. As another example in the classical case, the Yukawa interaction force $F_W = \frac{g^2 e^{-\alpha m r} (1 + \alpha m r)}{r^2}$, where g is the magnitude coupling constant and α is the coupling constant corresponding to the range of the interaction. For the Yukawa interaction to exceed the gravitational force, $\frac{g}{m} > \sqrt{\frac{G e^{\alpha m r}}{1 + \alpha m r}}$, which is still ambiguous in terms of the position-dependent lower bound, but the strictest lower bound is given by $\frac{g}{m} > \sqrt{G}$, in terms of some non-dimensionalising normalisation, which resembles the Coulombic case. This resemblance can be easily explained because the Coulombic fields or the mass of a photon $m = 0 \rightarrow F_W = F_E$, where the coupling constant $g = \frac{q}{\sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0}}$, which is reminiscent of

the missing normalisation. We proceed to see if in any given theory of quantum gravity, there exist such states with mass m that satisfy $m \lesssim gM_{Pl}$, M_{Pl} being the Planck mass and g being the coupling constant [1], the regime where the gauge repulsive forces are dominant over the gravitational attraction. It appears more relevant in the context of black hole decay kinematics [1] in a number of more generalised setups discussed in the sections below, mostly inspired from those of string theory.

It was conjectured for 4-dimensional theory with gravity and $U(1)$ gauge fields [1], both the electrical and magnetic counterparts; magnetic counterparts mathematically being Hodge-dual to the electrical charges. In [1], although it came across as “an anti-BPS” bound, this should not be mistaken to be the statement “*every possible charge should be satisfying the bound*”, but rather the case of the conjecture that there should be a state existing to satisfy it. There have been several preliminary evidences discussed in [1] without elaborate mathematical forerunning or infrastructure; $U(1)$ gauge fields from closed heterotic strings, Kaluza-Klein fields, 4D compactified type-I strings, Planck branes, $SO(32)$ heterotic strings compactified on T^6 (6-dimensional torus) etc. In a convenient normalisation, the weak gravity conjecture ultimately seeks for the particles with $\frac{M}{Q} \gtrsim 1$; [1] considered the naturalisation of Planck’s mass to go to unity. Now in the context of Gell-Mann’s totalitarian principle for black hole decays, there are the following three possibilities (as listed in verbatim in [1]):

1. $\left(\frac{M_{q_{\min}}}{q_{\min}}\right) \leq 1$, for the state of minimal charge.
2. $\left(\frac{M_{\min}}{q_{M_{\min}}}\right) \leq 1$, for the lightest charged particle.
3. $\left(\frac{M}{q}\right)_{\min} \leq 1$, for the particle with the smallest mass/charge ratio.

The conjectures 1 and 2 have been refuted when the lattice weak gravity conjecture is formulated in [2], as will be evident in the examples considered in section 4. There are some brief but convenient examples from string theory that have been exemplified in [1, 2]. Literature has been witness to propositions about these conjectures and their corresponding refutations. For example, in [1] where they consider weakly coupled $SO(32)$ heterotic strings, conjecture 1 would be violated for heavy half-integral charges, but has been contradicted with a counterexample in [2] which has been discussed in section 4.

In this article/report, some specific procedures such as dimensional reduction [2], leading to lattice weak gravity conjecture (LWGC) [6], WGC for axions and instantons [7, 8] (with some brief description on instantons [3, 4, 5]), and extensive compactification of manifolds leading to ramifications and considerations of LWGC.

2 Dimensional reduction

Verification of weak gravity conjecture for dilatonic fields coupled to p -form fields, radions with KK photons, $SO(32)$ heterotic strings, ADM decomposition of gravitational instantons coupled to p -form fields etc. has been discussed in [2]. I will demonstrate some detailed calculations for dilatonic fields coupled to p -form fields for a generic geometry reduced on a sphere S^{d-p-3} . To begin with, I would start with the action for a dilatonic field ϕ coupled

to p -form fields A_p , $F_{p+1} = dA_p \rightarrow (F_{p+1})_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_{p+1}} = \Sigma(-1)^k \partial_{\mu_k} A_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots}$,

$$S = \frac{1}{2\kappa_d^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} \left(R_d - \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi \right) - \frac{1}{2e_{p;d}^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} e^{-\alpha_{p;d} \phi} F_{p+1}^2 \quad (2)$$

Now if the metric g is dimensionally reduced to an $m = d - n = p + 3$ dimensional theory (with metric g) with the following, [18, 19]

$$g = \begin{pmatrix} h_{\mu\nu} e^{\frac{n\lambda(x)}{m-2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-\lambda(x)} \delta_{\mu\nu} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \sqrt{-\det(g)} = e^{\frac{n\lambda(x)}{d-n-2}} \sqrt{-\det(h)}$$

$$\rightarrow \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi = g_{\mu\nu} \partial^\mu \phi \partial^\nu \phi = e^{\frac{n\lambda}{d-n-2}} \sum_{\mu=1, \nu=1}^{d-n} h_{\mu\nu} \partial^\mu \phi \partial^\nu \phi + e^{-\lambda} \sum_{\mu=d-n+1}^d \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi$$

$$\rightarrow R_d = R_{d-n} + R_{S^n} = e^{-\frac{n\lambda}{d-n-2}} \left(R_{d-n}^{(h)} - \frac{d-1}{4(d-2)} h_{\mu\nu} \partial^\mu \lambda \partial^\nu \lambda \right)$$

which leads to the dimensionally reduced action that has been obtained in [2],

$$S = \frac{1}{2\kappa^2} \int d^m x \sqrt{-\det(h)} \left(R_{d-n}^{(h)} - \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi - \frac{n(d-2)}{4(d-n-2)} \partial_\mu \lambda \partial^\mu \lambda \right) - \frac{1}{2e_p^2} \left(\int d^m x \sqrt{-\det(h)} e^{-\alpha \phi - \frac{n(d-n-3)}{d-n-2} \lambda} F_{p+1}^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

The magnetic charges have been calculated with the definition for the same for a magnetic brane. The ADM tension for p -branes have been computed in (2.8) of [10] for a metric of the profile, a sort of a d -dimensional flat manifold embedded in a D -dimensional one,

$$ds^2 = -A(r) dt^2 + B(r) dr^2 + r^2 C(r) d\Omega_{D-d-1}^2 + A(r) \delta_{ij} dx^i dx^j \quad (4)$$

as,

$$M_d = -\frac{\text{vol}(\Omega_{D-d-1})}{2\kappa^2} \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} [(D-d-1)r^{D-d-1} \partial_r C(r) + (d-1)r^{D-d-1} \partial_r D(r) - (D-d-1)r^{D-d}(B(r) - C(r))] \quad (5)$$

which translates for an electrically charged black hole solution [2],

$$f_{\pm}(r) = 1 - \left(\frac{r_{\pm}}{r}\right)^p; \gamma = \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2} + \frac{p(d-p-2)}{d-2}\right)^{-1}; e^{-\alpha\phi} = f_-(r)^{\alpha^2\gamma}; F_{p+1} = \frac{e_{p;d}P}{\kappa_d\sqrt{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}(r_+r_-)^{\frac{\gamma}{2}}$$

$$ds^2 = -f_+(r)f_-(r)^{\frac{2p\gamma}{d-2}-1}dt^2 + \frac{f_-(r)^{\frac{\alpha^2\gamma}{p}-1}}{f_+(r)}dr^2 + r^2f_-(r)^{\frac{\alpha^2\gamma}{p}}d\Omega_{p+1}^2 + f_-(r)^{\frac{2p\gamma}{d-2}}\delta_{ij}dy^i dy^j$$

From which the magnetic charge Q_m and ADM tension T_m comes across as,

$$Q_m = \frac{p(r_+r_-)^{p/2}\sqrt{\gamma}}{g_{p;d}\kappa_d} \frac{2\pi^{\frac{p}{2}+1}}{\Gamma(\frac{p}{2}+1)}; T_m = \frac{(p+1)(r_+^p - r_-^p) + 2p\gamma r_-^p}{2\kappa_d^2} \frac{2\pi^{\frac{p}{2}+1}}{\Gamma(\frac{p}{2}+1)} \quad (6)$$

which leads to the extremality bound, $\gamma g_{p;d}^2 Q_m^2 < \kappa^2 T_m^2$. The weak gravity conjecture should be looking for particles of charge q and tension T_p that go beyond this bound to allow black holes to be able to decay; precisely,

$$\left[\frac{\alpha_{p;d}^2}{2} + \frac{p(d-p-2)}{d-2} \right] T_p^2 \leq e_{p;d}^2 q^2 M_d^{d-2} \quad (7)$$

To the above, [2] tried to check if the inequality is respected with dimensional reduction preserving d and changing p and also preserving p and reducing d , which relates to the LHS of the WGC just mentioned, which was well-proven in the case of toroidal compactification. To look for the satisfiability in the case of incorporating the change in q along p and d , a conveniently sought-for theory would be the Kaluza-Klein theory, which is quite motivational. As a good example, consider reducing on a circle of a radius R with a radion λ and a KK photon B_1 ,

$$ds^2 = e^{\frac{\lambda(x)}{d-2}} d\mathbf{s}^2 + e^{-\lambda(x)} (dy + RB_1)^2 \quad (8)$$

for which the original structure of the conjecture remains the same; $\left(\frac{\alpha_{KK}^2}{2} + \frac{d-3}{d-2}\right)m^2 \leq e_{KK}^2 q^2 M_d^{d-2}$, where $\alpha_{KK} = \sqrt{\frac{2(d-1)}{d-2}}$ and $e_{KK} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{RM_d^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}$, really boiling down to $m^2 \leq \frac{q^2}{R^2}$. Well

this is somewhat in contrast with the higher-dimensional KK-spectrum for a particle m_0 , $m^2 = m_0^2 + \frac{q^2}{R^2}$, $q \in \mathbb{Z}$. As is visible, the bound is exactly saturated for a massless particle, also consequently a graviphoton, but is not satisfied at all for massive particles. Nevertheless, it is shown [2] that both the electric and magnetic parts of the WGC is satisfied for the KK-photon. How about higher-form gauge fields? Higher-form gauge fields incorporate some

more flexibility in terms of inclusion of $U(1)$ charges. For example, consider the above circular reduction with a radion λ and KK photons with a 1-form,

$$F_2^{(D)} = G_2 + \frac{1}{2\pi} F_1 \wedge \left(\frac{dy}{R} + B_1 \right); A_1^{(D)} = A_1 + \frac{A_0}{2\pi} \left(\frac{dy}{R} + B_1 \right); f = \frac{1}{2\pi R e_d}$$

where f is the axion decay constant, A_0 being the axion, $F_1 = dA_0$ and $G_2 = dA_1 + \frac{A_0}{2\pi} H_2$. The dimensionally reduced action is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} S = & \frac{1}{2\kappa_d^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} \left(R_d - \frac{d-1}{4(d-2)} \partial_\mu \lambda \partial^\mu \lambda - \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi \right) \\ & - \frac{f^2}{2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} e^{-\alpha\phi + \lambda} \partial_\mu A_0 \partial^\mu A_0 - \frac{1}{2e_d^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} e^{-\alpha\phi - \frac{\lambda}{d-2}} |G_2|^2 \\ & - \frac{1}{2e_{KK}^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(g)} e^{-\frac{(d-1)\lambda}{(d-2)}} |H_2|^2 \end{aligned}$$

In [2], it has been computed that for ADM mass M , and the charges Q_F and Q_H , and background axion θ ,

$$M^2 \geq \gamma e_d^2 M_d^{d-2} Q_F^2 + \frac{1}{R^2} \left(Q_H - \frac{\theta}{2\pi} Q_F \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

A similar follow-through for 2-form fields gives more of a linear relation,

$$\kappa M \geq \sqrt{\gamma} e_d |Q_F| + \sqrt{\gamma_{KK}} e_{KK} |Q_{KK}| \quad (10)$$

There is a conventional normalisation in [2] for the charge-to-mass ratios of such particles which, for 2-form gauge fields forms an unstabilised diamond-shaped region outside the stabilised ellipsoidal region beyond the unit disk, whereas for 1-form gauge fields forms an ellipsoidal unstabilised region of charge-to-mass vectors that never touches the unit disk for a minimum radius in the charge-to-mass vector space (an issue very carefully resolved in [2]). This extremely important condition sought for the satisfiability, i.e. the ‘‘convex hull’’ of the charge-to-mass ratios of the particles coming from the decay of the black hole should contain the charge-to-mass ratios should contain the charge-to-mass ratios of all possible subextremal black holes, is known to be the convex hull condition. This actually motivates the reformulation of the weak gravity conjecture for charge lattices defined as the ‘‘lattice weak gravity conjecture (LWGC)’’, discussed in greater detail shown in section 4.

Rolling back a bit on axions, as an instance, the effective potential of a four-dimensional axion Wilsonlooped around a compactification breaks into an infinite series of instantons. This way, the WGC for gravitational instantons is also a sought-after attempt to address the same for axions. This will be addressed first in some detail in section 3.

The rest of the article has been bifurcated into two major subdivisions of weak gravity conjecture: the one for gravitational instantons in section 3 and the other for lattices of charges in section 4.

3 Weak gravity conjecture for gravitational instantons

Instantons were first discussed in [5], and introduced as a semi-classical limit to the quantum barrier penetration from the false vacuum to the next nearest zero of the potential; specifically probability of penetration per unit volume. In the semi-classical limit, using WKB approximation, it is easy to see the role of an exponential decay constant $U_B = \sqrt{8} \int_{q_0}^{\sigma} \sqrt{V_0(x)} dx$. For an easy toy-model example, consider a potential of the shape $V_0(x) = \lambda_U (x+A)^2(x-B)(x-C)$, $0 < A, 0 < B < C$. Simple algebraic geometry would reveal that $x = -A$ is a false vacuum, and $x = B$ is the next nearest zero-point energy prior to the true vacuum. Intuitionally, if it is possible that a particle to be given as much energy to penetrate until that point, it is highly likely to find a particle in true vacuum than the false vacua. The exponential decay constant in this case would be given as,

$$U_B(V_0) = \sqrt{8\lambda_U^2} \int_{-A}^B (x+A) \sqrt{(x-B)(x-C)} dx$$

$$\rightarrow U_B(V_0) = \sqrt{8\lambda_U^2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{(A+B)(A+C)}}{24} [4A^2 + 3B^2 + 3C^2 + 4AB + 4AC - 2BC] + \frac{(C-B)^2(2A+B+C)}{16} \log \left(\frac{(A+B)(A+C)}{C-B} \right) \right)$$

Each such triplet (A, B, C) reflects upon a different profile of the potential; only a specific set of such triplets is going to provide the least resistance to the particle to penetrate the barrier all through the way which can be done by computing the gradient and the Hessian matrix. This algorithm can be generalised on a very generic case when one can interpret this penetration exponential decay constant to be the Euclidean action itself. Some simpler cases have been discussed in [5]. When one translates the same for Lorentzian observers too, one observes that the case of “a bubble bouncing off the false vacuum” respects the same homotopies/isometries as that of the original theory, that follows from the correspondence between the penetration decay constant and the action, but at the same time, sees a rapid expansion in its size. There are some significant changes for general relativistic framework [4], which follows the same algebra as the classic case, but has some different conclusions of a smaller penetration probability. Cutting the long story short, gravitation reduces the probability of any particle going from false vacuum to true vacuum. As insightful it may sound, it does motivate one to look for quantum gravities that explain universal inflation from the one spot in the string theory landscape to the actual true vacuum of the universe. And as intuitional it may seem, this directly relates to the question whether weak gravity conjecture holds good enough for gravitational instantons.

Before we discuss the gravitational instantons, it is useful to establish a notion of the Bogomoln'yi bound [3]. Let us consider a $U(1)$ scalar field coupled to a photon by the following field theory,

$$\mathcal{L} = -(\partial_\mu - ieA_\mu)\phi(\partial^\mu + ieA^\mu)\phi^* - \frac{\lambda}{2}(|\phi|^2 - F^2)^2 - \frac{1}{4}F^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

The total energy of the theory is given as,

$$\begin{aligned} E &= \int d^n x \quad (\partial_\mu \phi)^2 + e^2 A^2 \phi^2 + \frac{1}{2} F_{12}^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} (|\phi|^2 - F^2)^2 \\ &= \int d^n x \quad (\partial_\mu \phi \pm e \epsilon_{\mu\nu} A^\nu \phi)^2 \mp e \epsilon_{\mu\nu} \partial^\mu (\phi^2 A^\nu) \pm e \phi^2 F_{12} + \frac{1}{2} (F_{12} \pm \sqrt{\lambda} (\phi^2 - F^2))^2 \mp \sqrt{\lambda} (\phi^2 - \\ &F^2) F_{12} \\ &\rightarrow E \geq e F^2 \left| \int d^n x F_{12} \right|, \lambda = e^2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

This inequality above is the Bogomoln'yi bound. There are similar bounds for non-Abelian gauge theories too (also coupled to photons) and the states that satisfy the Bogomoln'yi-Prasad-Sommerfeld or the BPS bound are known as the BPS states. But if we consider just the non-Abelian gauge or Yang-Mills fields, then there are two specific types of ‘‘Bogomoln'yi saturators’’: $F_{\mu\nu} = F_{\mu\nu}^t$ (F^t fields being dual to the F fields) and $F_{\mu\nu} = -F_{\mu\nu}^t$; both of them satisfying the Bianchi identity $D^\mu F_{\mu\nu} = 0, D^\mu F_{\mu\nu}^t = 0$ where $D_\mu = \partial_\mu - igT^a A_\mu^a$, T^a being the generator of the Lie algebra to be used in context, $F = dA$, and g being the coupling constant. The former usually are referred to as the ‘‘instantons’’ and the latter, ‘‘anti-instantons’’.

The gravitational instantons [2, 8, 9] come in three classes: Euclidean wormhole solutions, the ‘‘extremal’’ flat metric and the ones with a singular core. The metric for a d -dimensional gravitational instantons has a generic structure as follows [2]

$$ds^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 + \zeta \left(\frac{r_0}{r}\right)^{2(d-2)}} + r^2 \Omega_{d-1}^2 \quad (13)$$

where ζ is 0 for the extremal case, 1 for Euclidean wormholes and -1 for cored singularities. Some geodesic structures for verification have been computed and presented in [19]. [1] just mentioned that the instanton action is empirically inversely proportional to the axion decay constant in the Planckian scale, which was elaborately shown in both the [2] and [8] to be $S_{\text{inst}} = \frac{2\sqrt{2}\pi Q}{e\kappa a}, \alpha \geq \alpha_0$; $\frac{2\sqrt{2}\pi Q}{e\kappa\alpha_0} \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha}{\alpha_0} - 1}, \alpha < \alpha_0$, α_0 being the critical coupling. Also [2] and [8] computed the instanton potentials in slightly different ways. [2] showed, in their dimensional reduction framework, $\gamma g_{d-2; d}^2 Q^2 \leq \kappa^2 S_{\text{inst}}^2$, which has been reconfirmed using actual dimensional reduction after physically boundary around the manifold using

the Gibbons-Hawking-York surface term. Equation (7.5) of [8] seems to refute the weak gravity conjecture after some refinements such as testing it for large-sized Kahler moduli, compactified axio-dilaton, maximal field displacements, large field inflation limit etc. The overall status of the weak gravity conjecture for gravitational instantons and axions is thus still under debate [7, 8, 9] in terms of theoretical consistency and soundness, even though having some prospective applications into fields like algebraic geometry [11]. As an example of future work, it would be really interesting to see the weak gravity conjecture for the decay of a single core gravitational instanton into a multiple such singularities, and also for the space of “Dehn surgical instantons”: tubes of manifolds after the Dehn surgery of the cores. Dehn surgery is defined for a 3-manifold: Given a 3-manifold M and a link $L \subset M$, the manifold M is drilled along L by removing an open tubular neighbourhood from M , and then a solid torus is glued in by means of an appropriate homeomorphism of its boundary to the boundary of the drilled link.

4 Lattice and sublattice weak gravity conjecture

In section 2, the dimensional reduction onto a circle of radius R with radion λ coupled to 1-form gauge field A_1 does satisfy the weak gravity conjecture but originally violates the convex hull condition but can be fixed using arguments from the description of the effective field theory and assumptions of high cutoff despite additional charged particles. There are many examples in string theory with this property. So another potentially strong formulation of the weak gravity conjecture is that

“For every point \vec{Q} on the charge lattice, there is a particle of charge \vec{Q} with charge-to-mass ratio at least as that of a large, semi-classical, non-rotating extremal black hole with $\vec{Q}_{\text{BH}} \propto \vec{Q}$ ”

The above is known as the lattice weak gravity conjecture. In the examples discussed in [2], the above implies the convex hull condition and is preserved under toroidal compactification. To begin with, a lattice in \mathbb{R}^n is a subgroup of the additive group \mathbb{R}^n which is isomorphic to the additive group \mathbb{Z}^n spanning \mathbb{R}^n . Lattices can be defined for any general vector spaces too: Let K be a field, V be an n -dimensional K -vector space, $B = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ be a K -basis for V and let R be a ring, $R \subseteq K$. Then R -lattice \mathcal{L} in V generated by B is given by

$$\mathcal{L} = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \vec{v}_i \mid a_i \in R, \vec{v}_i \in B \right\} \quad (14)$$

For a vector space which is also an inner product space, the dual lattice can be described by the set

$$\mathcal{L}^* = \{ \vec{v} \in V \mid \langle \vec{v}, \vec{x} \rangle \in R, \forall \vec{x} \in \mathcal{L} \} \quad (15)$$

As has been mentioned in section 1, [1] showed in three possibilities of which two conjectures emerged as the candidates: the conjecture for the lightest charged particle and the conjecture for the smallest mass/charge ratio. Clearly, LWGC is logically consistent with the both the

conjectures. [2] evaluates the LWGC for $SO(32)$ heterotic string theory whose effective action is given by,

$$S = \frac{1}{2\kappa_{10}^2} \int d^{10}x \sqrt{-\det(g)} e^{-2\Phi} \left(R + 4\partial_\mu \Phi \partial^\mu \Phi - \frac{\kappa_{10}^2}{g_{10}^2} \text{Tr}_V(|F_2|^2) \right) \quad (16)$$

where Tr_V is the trace in the fundamental representation. The $SO(32)$ spinor for the Cartan in ten dimensions at the first excited level $m^2 = \frac{4}{\alpha'}$ in the heterotic string theory has 2^{15} states with charge vectors,

$$\vec{q} = \left(\pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \dots, \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) \rightarrow |\vec{q}|^2 = 16 \times \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^2 = 4 \quad (17)$$

The charge lattice of the $SO(32)$ heterotic string consists of all the charge vectors of the form:

$$\vec{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_{16}) \text{ or } \vec{q} = \left(q_1 + \frac{1}{2}, q_2 + \frac{1}{2}, \dots, q_{16} + \frac{1}{2} \right), q_i \in \mathbb{Z}, \sum_i q_i \in 2\mathbb{Z} \quad (18)$$

Coming from the arguments based on the on-shell mass spectrum and level matching, [2] showed that the weak gravity conjecture does not look for the lightest charged particle at all. In this specific example, the lightest charged particle lies outside the region of stabilisation. As an another example, consider the case of k -toroidal compactification with a general metric ansatz [6]

$$ds_D^2 = (\det(\varphi))^{\frac{-1}{d-2}} g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu + R^2 \varphi_{ij} (d\theta^i + A_\mu^i dx^\mu) (d\theta^j + A_\nu^j dx^\nu) \quad (19)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}$ denotes the $d = D - k$ dimensional metric, φ_{ij} the $\frac{k(k+1)}{2}$ metric moduli, A_μ^i the graviphotons, and R^2 the overall compactification. The fields $g_{\mu\nu}$, φ_{ij} , A_μ^i expressed in terms of plane waves in T^k ,

$$\varphi_{ij}(x, \theta) = \sum_{\vec{n} \in \mathbb{Z}^k} \varphi^{(\vec{n})}(x) e^{i \sum_i \theta_i n^i} \quad (20)$$

and similarly for $g_{\mu\nu}$ and A_μ^i . The dimensionally reduced action for the zero modes $\hat{\varphi} = \varphi^{(\vec{0})}$,

$$S = \frac{1}{2\kappa_d^2} \int d^d x \sqrt{-\det(\hat{g})} \left(\mathcal{R}[\hat{g}] - \frac{1}{4} \left[\hat{\varphi}^{ik} \hat{\varphi}^{jl} + \frac{1}{d-2} \hat{\varphi}^{ij} \hat{\varphi}^{kl} \right] \nabla \hat{\varphi}_{ij} \cdot \nabla \hat{\varphi}_{kl} - \frac{R^2}{2} \left(\det(\hat{\varphi})^{\frac{1}{d-2}} \right) \hat{\varphi}_{ij} \hat{F}^i \cdot \hat{F}^j \right) \quad (21)$$

where $\hat{\varphi}^{ij}\hat{\varphi}_{jk} = \delta_k^i$. The extremality bound was proven to be $M^2 \geq \hat{\varphi}^{ij} \frac{Q_i Q_j}{R^2}$, Q_i being charges which are actually mode numbers, which is well within LWGC. But if we fold the torus into a simple orbifold, things change quite drastically [6]. For example, consider a compactification on $T^3/(\mathbb{Z}_2 \times \mathbb{Z}'_2)$ with the following symmetries,

$$\mathbb{Z}_2: \theta_w \rightarrow \theta_w + \pi, \theta_y \rightarrow \theta_y + \pi \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}'_2: \theta_w \rightarrow -\theta_w, \theta_z \rightarrow \theta_z + \pi \quad (23)$$

which resembles something like how a Klein bottle looks like. The mode decomposition of a field ϕ on the T^3 is given by $\phi(x^\mu, \theta_w, \theta_y, \theta_z) = \sum \phi_{n_x, n_y, n_z}(x^\mu) e^{i(n_w \theta_w + n_y \theta_y + n_z \theta_z)}$. The group action imposes the following:

$$\mathbb{Z}_2: \phi_{n_x, n_y, n_z}(x) = (-1)^{n_w + n_y} \phi_{n_x, n_y, n_z}(x) \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}'_2: \phi_{n_x, n_y, n_z}(x) = (-1)^{n_z} \sigma(\phi) \phi_{n_x, n_y, n_z}(x) \quad (25)$$

where $\sigma(\phi)$ denotes an additional sign that depends on the nature of the field ϕ . If n_y is even and n_z is even, the symmetry of ϕ in \mathbb{Z}_2 depends on the parity in n_w , moreover, the mode of the graviton is saturated with smallest even n_w , i.e. $n_w = 0$. If n_y is even and n_z is odd, the saturation happens with $\sigma(\phi) = -1$ and $n_w = 0$. But there are more uncertainties with the n_y being odd, due to which no superextremal modes exists, leading to violation of LWGC. But a proper sublattice with even n_y does satisfy WGC. Thus comes another formulation of WGC in terms of sublattices, known as the ‘‘Sublattice Weak Gravity Conjecture’’ [6].

‘‘For a theory with charge lattice Γ , there exists a sublattice $\Gamma_{\text{ext}} \subseteq \Gamma$ of finite coarseness such that for each $\vec{q} \in \Gamma_{\text{ext}}$, there is a (possibly unstable) superextremal particle of charge \vec{q} .’’

where the coarseness of a sublattice $\Gamma_{\text{ext}} \subseteq \Gamma$ is the smallest integer N such that $N\vec{q} \in \Gamma_{\text{ext}}$ for any $\vec{q} \in \Gamma$. As an example, let us consider NSNS sector gauge fields in the worldsheet CFT [6], which has a partition function of the form,

$$Z(\mu, \bar{\mu}; \tau, \bar{\tau}) = \text{Tr}(q^\Delta \bar{q}^{\tilde{\Delta}} y^Q \bar{y}^{\tilde{Q}}) \quad (26)$$

where $\Delta = L_0 - \frac{c}{2\pi}$, $\tilde{\Delta} = \tilde{L}_0 - \frac{\tilde{c}}{2\pi}$, $q = e^{2\pi i \tau}$, $y = e^{2\pi i \mu}$, where Q and \tilde{Q} are conserved currents in right-movers and left-movers respectively. We have $Z(\mu + \rho) = Z(\mu)$, $\forall \rho \in \Gamma_Q^*$, Γ_Q^* being the dual charge lattice $\Gamma_Q^* = \{(\rho, \tilde{\rho}) | \rho Q - \tilde{\rho} \tilde{Q} \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. The modular invariance requires

$$Z(\mu; \tau + 1) = Z(\mu; \tau), Z\left(\frac{\mu}{\tau}; -\frac{1}{\tau}\right) = e^{i\frac{\pi}{\tau}(k\mu^2 - \tilde{k}\bar{\mu}^2)} Z(\mu; \tau) \quad (27)$$

Algebraically composing the periodicity and modular invariance yields $Z(\mu + \tau\rho, \tau) = \exp(-2\pi i k \mu \rho - \pi i k \rho^2 \tau + 2\pi i \tilde{k} \tilde{\mu} \tilde{\rho}) Z(\mu, \tau)$. So with this, if we define $T = \Delta - \frac{Q^2}{2}$ and similarly the “tilded”-counterparts, $Z(\mu, \tilde{\mu}; \tau, \tilde{\tau}) = \text{Tr}(q^{T+Q^2/2} \tilde{q}^{\tilde{T}+\tilde{Q}^2/2} y^Q \tilde{y}^{\tilde{Q}})$ which leads to translational symmetry $Q \rightarrow Q + \rho$ and $\tilde{Q} \rightarrow \tilde{Q} + \tilde{\rho}$. With all this, it can be concluded that with modular invariance leads to $\Gamma_Q^* \subseteq \Gamma_Q$, thus satisfying the sublattice WGC. Similarly, it has been proven that $E_8 \times E_8$ heterotic compactification on T_4/\mathbb{Z}_2 with Wilson lines [6] does not satisfy LWGC, but satisfies sLWGC with coarseness 2. Similarly, sLWGC is satisfied for T^4/\mathbb{Z}_3 heterotic orbifold with Wilson lines with coarseness 3.

Also, it is very useful to know if the sLWGC holds good for Ricci-flat manifolds with KK theory. It can be generalised from the sLWGC on compactification to T^k/G_0 [6], where G_0 is a freely acting finite group of translations and rotations on T^k . Using a projection map $\Pi: V \rightarrow \frac{1}{|G_0|} \sum_{g \in G_0} gV$, it can be proven that the Killing vectors of T^k close and the invariant and null subspaces generate subtori $T^p \subset T^k$ and $T^{k-p} \subset T^k$ respectively. Thus, for some a discrete translation group H , $T^k = \frac{T^p \times T^{k-p}}{H}$, and thus consequently, $\frac{T^k}{G_0} = \frac{T^p \times M'_{k-p}}{G}$, where M'_{k-p} is a smooth toroidal orbifold and G acts by simultaneous translations on T^p combined with certain discrete isometries of M'_{k-p} . When proving that sLWGC holds in the d -dimensional pure gravity compactified on T^k/G_0 , one realises that the group G defines a lattice $\Gamma_G \supseteq \mathbb{Z}^p$ via $T^p/G \cong \mathbb{R}^p/G$ where each element of $g \in G$ corresponds to a coset $\mathbb{Z}^p + \vec{g}$ within Γ_G and Γ_G^* is contained in the Γ_G lattice having all the extremal particles. For a generalised Ricci-flat manifold M_k , the factorisation just becomes $M_k = \frac{T^p \times M'_{k-p}}{G}$ where G is a finite freely acting group combining the translational subgroup of T^p with a direct isometry group of M'_{k-p} , and the rest just follows in similitude.

4.1 Computability of sublattice WGC in homology spheres

In this subsection, a part of the motivation that comes correlations between computability theory and differential geometry brought about in [12]. We begin with some essential definitions that are necessary to discuss the result of the relationships, the definitions that are required to state the theorem of those “correlations”. The homology of a topological space X is a set of topological invariants of X represented by the homology groups $H_0(X), H_1(X), \dots, H_n(X), \dots$ where the k^{th} homology group $H_k(X)$ informally describes the presence of k -dimensional holes in X . For a trivial example, $H_k(S^n) = \mathbb{Z}$, for $k=0, n$ and is $\{0\}$ otherwise. A more formal definition of the homology groups requires a topological construction. A chain complex is a sequence of abelian groups or modules C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots connected by homeomorphisms $\partial_n: C_n \rightarrow C_{n-1}$ which are called boundary operators, represented by the following chain:

$$\dots \rightarrow \partial_{n+1} C_n \rightarrow \partial_n C_{n-1} \rightarrow \partial_{n-1} C_{n-2} \rightarrow \partial_{n-2} \dots \rightarrow \partial_2 C_1 \rightarrow \partial_1 C_0 \rightarrow \partial_0 0$$

Elements of $B_n(X) = \text{im}(\partial_{n+1})$ are called boundaries and elements of $Z_n(X) = \text{ker}(\partial_n)$ are called cycles. The n^{th} homology group is defined by $H_n(X) = Z_n(X)/B_n(X)$ and its elements the homology classes. An n -homology sphere is an n -manifold X having the homology groups of an n -sphere, i.e. $H_0(X) = H_n(X) = \mathbb{Z}$ and $H_k(X) = \{0\}$ for all other $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Examples of some homology spheres include surgeries on a knot in a 3-sphere [15], Brieskorn 3-sphere [17] and some selected Seifert fiber spaces [16]. A connected sum of two m -dimen-

sional manifolds A and B , denoted as $A\#B$, is informally defined as following: a portion (really a ball) of the two manifolds each is deleted and the two holes are joined by the resulting boundary sphere. Given a Riemannian manifold and two linearly independent tangent vectors u and v , the sectional curvature $K(u, v)$ is defined as

$$K(u, v) = \frac{\langle R(u, v)v, u \rangle}{\langle u, u \rangle \langle v, v \rangle - \langle u, v \rangle^2} \quad (28)$$

where $R(u, v)$ is the Riemannian curvature tensor and $\langle a, b \rangle$ is the inner product norm. A simplicial norm would be for a simplicial complex along with a well-defined inner product. Informally, a simplicial complex is a set of points, line segments, triangles and n -dimensional counterparts of triangles for $n > 3$. The set of diffeomorphisms/isometries of a manifold M forms a group, known as $\text{Diff}(M)$, and the set of Riemannian metrics on the manifold M also forms a group, known as $\text{Riem}(M)$. Quotienting the former from the latter yields $\text{Met}(M) = \text{Riem}(M)/\text{Diff}(M)$, signifying a ‘‘metrizable’’ manifold.

Now come the requisite definitions from computability theory. For enumerating discrete structures and Turing machines, I would denote the set \mathbb{N} by the set ω . Let $\{P_e\}_\omega$ be an effective indexing of all Turing machines. We define $\varphi_e(x) = y$ if P_e with input x eventually halts with output y , and $\varphi_{e,s}(x) = y$ if $\varphi_e(s) = y$ in less than s steps of P_e and $x, y, e < s$. A set S is computably enumerable if there exists a Turing machine M such that $M(x) = 1$ if $x \in S$ and M does not halt if $x \notin S$. Let $W_e = \text{domain}(\varphi_e)$ be the e^{th} computable enumerable set. The set $\{W_e | e \in \omega\}$ is defined as the Kleene listing of all the computably enumerable set. The μ -operator is also roughly defined for a unary relation $R(y)$ as follows: the μ -operator ‘‘ μy ’’ in either the bounded or the unbounded form is a function mapping from \mathbb{N} to \mathbb{N} ; if $\exists y, y < z, R(y)$, $\mu y_{y < z} R(y)$ is the least $y < z$ such that $R(y)$, else $\mu y_{y < z} R(y) = z$. There are more generalised definitions for this operator in the literature [13, 20]. But for each W_e , the partial computable halting function is defined as $\theta_e(x) = \{(\mu s)[x \in W_{e,s}]\}$, if s exists, else the corresponding Turing machine does not halt. Finally, we define the settling function, $\sigma_e(x) = \max \{\theta_e(y) : y < x \text{ where } \theta_e(y) \text{ halts}\}$.

Now one is ready to state what Nabutovsky and Weinberger proved about the computability of a specific sequence of homology spheres [14]. Let M be a smooth, compact manifold of dimension $n \geq 5$ and sectional curvature $|K| \leq 1$. Nabutovsky and Weinberger proved that for every $n \geq 5$, there is an effective sequence $\{P_k\}_{k \in \omega}$ of n -homology spheres such that $\forall k$, either P_k is diffeomorphic to S^n or the simplicial norm $\|P_k\| > 1$, and that the set $S = \{k | P_k \approx_{\text{dif}} S^n\}$ is computably enumerable and the set $T = \{k | \|P_k\| > 1\}$ is not computably enumerable, where the relation \approx_{dif} denotes ‘‘is diffeomorphic to’’, and also S and T are disjoint. Consequently, [12, 14] ‘‘for every Turing machine $T_e, e \in \omega$, there exists a sequence of n -homology spheres $\{P_k^e\}_{k \in \omega} \approx_{\text{dif}} S^n$ iff T_e halts on input k , and in this case, the connected sum $N_k^e = M \# P_k^e$ is also diffeomorphic to M and N_k^e is associated with a local minimum of diameter function on $\text{Met}(M)$ whose depth is roughly equal to the settling time $\sigma_e(k)$ of T_e on inputs $y < k$.’’ The proof actually includes a ‘‘melding procedure’’ [14] which is the core of the actual potential computation in the process of enumeration. The melding algorithm is briefly the following: begin with a d -homology sphere Σ and consider all the generators g_i of its torsion-free fundamental group. For each of these generators, we take the connected sum of Σ and a copy $\Sigma^n(T, \omega)$, construction of which has again been briefly described in section 9 of [14].

As mentioned above, sLWGC holds good for Kaluza-Klein theory arising from pure gravity compactified to arbitrary Ricci-flat manifolds, i.e. there exists a sublattice of the charge

lattice in this theory where for all the charges of the sublattice, there is a superextremal particle of that charge. Since the set of n -homology spheres that are diffeomorphic to a standard sphere (which are also Ricci-flat) is computably enumerable, there exists an algorithm (that does not necessarily halt) to list down a sequence of such homology spheres. Both of these lead to a natural conclusion that the set of superextremal particles of the charges in the sublattice that actually arise in the context of sLWGC for any sequence of these Ricci-flat homology spheres is also computably enumerable, i.e. there exists an algorithm to figure out these superextremal particles. As an inspired future work, it would be interesting to see if there is an algorithm that finds this sequence of superextremal particles which does not perform the trivial brute-force or trial-and-error checks. Also, it would be definitely be interesting to see if sublattice WGC holds good for computably enumerable topological spaces [21] which would mean that there can be algorithms to find the set of superextremal particles, or even that the algorithms that assure that such particles do exist. As a broader question to ask, it would be interesting to see if the set of theories satisfying the conjecture is computably enumerable or not, thus reducing the effort to prove them by a significant margin.

5 Conclusion

This article begins with the definition of weak gravity conjecture for quantum gravities and some elementary examples from classical theories and motivates one to explore the same with some earlier established theories coupled to the Einstein-Hilbert theory. Dimensional reduction seems to be an indispensable tool to look for sub-extremal particles when the theory is compactified on some simple geometries such as standard spheres, both in neutral and KK-charged realms. Violation of the original formulation of WGC, actually the convex hull condition, in the case of 2-form gauge fields coupled to the reduced compactification in the most raw form motivates the proposition of lattice weak gravity conjecture, which states that every point in the charge lattice should possess a subextremal particle, which holds well enough in the case of examples such as heterotic string theory and toroidal compactifications. However, only some sectors of lattice seem to satisfy the lattice WGC in the case of toroidal orbifolds resembling the “Klein bottle” geometries, thus motivating another reformulation: the sublattice WGC. Emergence of sLWGC from notions such as Ricci-flatness and modular invariance have been discussed. A new germination of a theory in terms of computability of the superextremal charges in the sublattices has been established. Another realm of WGC is for the gravitational instantons has also been discussed in some detail, including a brief background of the classical instantons, gravitational instantons, Bogomoln’yi and BPS bounds, and finally, some brief debate about the conclusions about the status of the conjecture. Literature has been witness to the relationship of the weak gravity conjecture with the other contemporary problems such as swampland distance conjecture, AdS distance conjecture, QCD axion quality problem etc. but pure clarity about the description and validation of its own entity is at some distance from the present.

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